

R3PACK – REDUCE, REUSE, RETHINK PACKAGING TOWARDS NOVEL FIBER-BASED PACKAGING AND REUSE SCHEMES

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the Action Plan (Work Package 7 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation through replication, policy Dialogue and capacity building) of the R3PACK project (Grant Agreement n° 101060806).

The main objective of this Action Plan is to provide all project partners with an outline that covers: (1) the target groups the project seeks to impact, (2) the main messages of the project, (3) the actions to be carried out to reach them, (4) the general and specific obligations regarding Dissemination and Communication of the project that all partners must be aware of and (5) the Advocacy Strategy.

(1) Key target groups for the project are packaging manufacturers, brand owners & retailers, experts and scientists, policy makers, civil society & consumers, and investors.

(2) Apart from the generic messages, each target group counts with its own tailored messages. Moreover, the document also directly identifies potential future project results relevant for dissemination.

(3) The Dissemination and Communication actions are part of an online and offline strategy that includes: press releases; a project webpage; social media accounts; mass media publications; production of audio-visual materials (flyers, roll-up, leaflets, infographics); scientific publications; sectorial and academic events; actions with policy makers, and a final event. On the other hand, there are specific actions targeted to different audiences.

(4) Obligations related to Communication & Dissemination cover visibility of funding, the figure of the Communications Representative, notifications, minimum communication actions expected of each partner and basic visual guidelines.

(5) The Advocacy Strategy will develop on actions (press releases, position papers) to support policy change at EU level promoting alternative sustainable packaging and the uptake of reuse schemes.

Regarding knowledge management and ethics, this document offers a broad overview of the main points to consider and refers to the specific deliverables that tackle this topic.

Minimum support in communication actions is expected from each partner, as well as support in developing R3PACK's advocacy strategy.

To sum up, this document describes and presents the most relevant aspects of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy as well as Advocacy Strategy of the R3PACK project, establishes responsibilities and timings, and includes practical examples for the different cases.

INTRODUCTION

Scope of the document

This document describes the Action Plan on dissemination, communication and advocacy for the R3PACK project, identifying and targeting a wide array of audiences from industry, to academia, investors, civil society and European institutions. It covers the actions that will be carried out for the achievements of the objectives raised in the Grant Agreement, notably with regard to Work Package (WP) 7 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation through replication, policy Dialogue and capacity building.

The Action Plan is the core document outlining the project's dissemination and communication activities. This plan is fundamental for a good coordination of project output dissemination, as only effective communication will allow visibility of results and encourage interested stakeholders to actively participate. **The Action Plan is also the core document outlining R3PACK's advocacy strategy.** Coordination to develop the actions described therein are essential to attain the advocacy objectives of R3PACK.

This document has been prepared by SAFE – Safe Food Advocacy Europe, WP7 leader. The WP leader will be responsible for overseeing the implementation, coordination and execution of the actions included in this document, alongside the partners involved in WP7 as laid down in the Grant Agreement.

Objectives of this work package

WP7 will run from M1 to M36. The aim of WP7 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation through replication, policy Dialogue and capacity building – is to maximise the impact of the project through:

- Efficient dissemination and communication activities targeting industrials, academic, EU investors and policymakers, environmental stakeholders, civil society and the general public;
- A clear business case and exploitation strategy to scale up R3PACK's innovations at EU level, and replicate them to different relevant sectors, beyond food packaging;
- Igniting policy-change by advocating for a reduction of material complexity in material use, supporting the transition towards paper based packaging and rapid and enhanced uptake of industrial reuse schemes through the introduction of suitable targets.
- Provide a database of contacts for the newsletter, taking into account GDPR compliance.

List of partners involved in communication

All 24 partners will be involved in WP7. These are:

1. (RE)SET
2. RISE
3. Fraunhofer
4. CNR-ISTC
5. INNOVHUB
6. UNIBO
7. POLIMI
8. AU
9. BIM Kemi AB
10. BIOEXTRAX
11. SAFE
12. SGS
13. CARREFOUR
14. U ENSEIGNE
15. EUROPE SNACKS
16. ALTHO
17. LSDH
18. FLOREALE HO
19. CANDIA
20. GASCOGNE
21. GUILLIN
22. Thiolat
23. SCHREIBER
24. Fiberlean

Partner's involvement

Partners are expected to help:

- Disseminate project results and outputs towards the scientific community, food industries and associations, retailing industries, policymakers, financial institutions and investors
- Engage with consumers through offline channels (in store booklets and retailers' printed materials, dedicated events and campaigns) and online channels (social media, project website, newsletter).
- Participating in relevant conferences; stakeholders' and demonstrators' workshops
- Contributing to scientific publications and popular sciences articles
- Participate in stakeholder and demonstrator workshops.

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

1. TARGET AUDIENCES

Major efforts will be given to securing a continuous two-way communication (online and offline) with interested actors and identified target groups, namely through participatory activities. The communication activities will aim to effectively involve all stakeholders, end-users and the general public to contribute to R3PACK successful implementation.

Based on the project objectives, SAFE divides the audience into 7 groups:

1. Packaging manufacturers
2. Industrials (food producers (brand owners), including retailers with own-brands)
3. Retailers
4. Experts and scientists
5. Policy makers
6. Civil society & consumers
7. Investors

SAFE aims to adapt dissemination actions to each audience. Thus, during the time of the WP7 (M1-M36), SAFE plans the connect with the following groups:

1.1. PACKAGING MANUFACTURERS

Packaging manufacturers have a crucial role for the further uptake of the innovations proposed. All dissemination efforts will aim to show the future returns in terms of economic and environmental innovation to advance the global uptake of the developed innovative models. SAFE will provide media coverage for the project and promote the new sustainable solutions developed by it. To achieve this goal, SAFE will interact with this targeted group in order to get updates on the R&D and scientific inputs to be used for communication materials.

Packaging manufacturers will be invited to participate in all 8 organised during project implementation (events: 6 webinars, 1 workshop, and 1 final conference (Further details at pages 25-27). The latter, the Stakeholder and Final event in Brussels, will be organised for M32 and is expected to regroup about 500 participants, both online and offline. Besides, they will be invited to a Stakeholder Workshop that will be organised in Brussels in M30, with academics, policy makers and the civil society. The workshop will be also accessible online and recorded to maximise the dissemination through European key stakeholders.

1.2. INDUSTRIALS (FOOD PRODUCERS (BRAND-OWNERS), INCLUDING RETAILERS WITH OWN-BRANDS)

Industrials are also important to contact. They will play a part into the further uptake of the innovations proposed, and their inputs will be used to demonstrate future economic returns and environmental innovation of R3PACK. The communication activities of R3PACK will rely largely on the capacity of the brand owners involved to increase project visibility and consumer outreach via in-store (for retailers) communication on project results and sustainability goal. This offline communication will allow to raise consumer awareness on the topic of plastic-free and reusable food packaging.

Industrials will be invited to participate in all 8 events organised, including the Stakeholder Workshop that will be organised in Brussels (M30). Finally, they will be invited to the Stakeholder and Final event in Brussels (M32 - Milestone 12).

1.3. RETAILERS

Retailers are key actors of the food value chain and must be involved to lead the transition to sustainability by promoting a fundamental rethinking of their delivery chains. They can define strategies and set ambitious targets to promote plastic reduction and reuse of packaging. To develop our packaging solutions at a large scale, we need retailers to be involved. Retailers are also important stakeholders to communicate to in order to effectively reach consumers.

Communication and dissemination efforts will aim to show the future returns in terms of economic and environmental innovation of the packaging solutions developed.

Retailers will be targeted by our online communication. They will also be invited to participate in all 8 events organised, including the Stakeholder Workshop (M30) and the Stakeholder and Final event (M32 - Milestone 12).

1.4. EXPERTS AND SCIENTISTS

Experts and scientists have led the way in making plastic pollution a high-profile issue for policymakers and businesses alike. R3PACK will bring ground-breaking evolutions on the packaging industry. All the dedicated research community will be widely reached by SAFE on the project results and specifically targeted for that.

The experts and scientists group includes Technological Centres, researchers, and universities in Europe. The exchange of knowledge and lessons learnt with academic audiences will benefit the research community, facilitating deeper understanding of the processes developed. The goal is to target audiences able to use and implement the research work developed by the project beyond the duration of R3PACK.

Regarding scientific publications, at least 10 articles will be published in scientific journals to present the outstanding results that are expected to be obtained in the R3PACK project. Open Research Europe platform will be used to allow a wide and open access to the project peer-reviewed scientific publications.

Virtual roundtables and events, featuring project partners, will be organised to disseminate scientific knowledge beyond the consortium. Experts and scientists will also be invited to the Stakeholder Workshop (M30) and to the Stakeholder and Final event (M32 - Milestone 12).

1.5. POLICY MAKERS

The R3PACK project will contribute with sector-specific knowledge to the policy topics concerning packaging, environment, sustainability, and innovation.

To effectively maximise the impact of this knowledge development, it will be necessary to target specific relevant policy figures regarding packaging and innovation in Europe, who are able to impact policy towards packaging waste.

The goal of establishing a solid connection with policy makers is to build synergies with the other key funded projects of the Green Deal call, as well as with other relevant regional / national / EU projects, and importantly, establishing a combined coordination with the European Commission bodies and established platforms, targeted to maximise the impact of this action.

Policy makers will be reached thanks to active communication via advocacy actions. SAFE will develop policy papers, articles, and press releases in line with the most relevant legislative initiatives. Also, they will be invited to the 8 events organised by the consortium to promote the project and disseminate its results. They will notably be invited to the Stakeholder Workshop (M30) and to the Stakeholder and Final event (M32 - Milestone 12).

SAFE, the leader of WP7 has compiled in M2 a specific mapping file compiling over 800 relevant stakeholders made available internally via R3PACK's team channel. Further information on these mapping can be found in Appendix I. The latter includes:

- At the European Parliament:
 - Committee AGRI
 - Committee IMCO
 - Committee ENVI
- At the European Commission:
 - DG SANTE
 - DG ENVI
 - DG CLIMATE
 - DG GROW
- Permanent Representations
 - Sectoral representatives and attachés of EU27 Member States

1.6. CIVIL SOCIETY & CONSUMERS

Consumer awareness of packaging waste and their environmental and social externalities constitute driving factors of change. Consumer acceptance and active participation in the transition is key to secure the success of R3PACK solutions. Consumer demand has played and should continue to play a catalytic role in accelerating the change.

Communication towards citizens and consumers will be organised both through offline and online channels, such as via the creation of a dedicated Instagram account.

SAFE being a member-based consumers organisation, we will reach to our members active in the field of packaging to disseminate R3PACK results. SAFE is also a member of the Food Policy Coalition and thus will use the mean of communication too.

1.7. INVESTORS

R3PACK will directly target investors to inform them about the benefits of the developed solutions and promote the development of specific investment vehicles such as seed funding in the form of grants, blended/concessional capital while prioritising dissemination facilitating technical assistance and introduction to additional relevant industry players.

Demonstrator workshops will also be organised at the demonstration sites to engage local, regional and European private and public investors and further maximise R3PACK impact.

2. MESSAGES

2.1. WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF R3PACK?

Packaging waste accounts for 36% of solid waste in EU towns, with plastics being the most widely used material in European food retail, covering 37% of food sold. Recent research shows that important reductions can be achieved by focusing on six plastic applications that are projected to account for 86% of the total reduction achievable by 2040, with multilayer/multimaterial packaging constituting the biggest untapped potential. Consumer awareness of packaging waste and their environmental and social externalities is driving change, while major brands encounter difficulties in self-regulating, as they lack innovative solutions immediately applicable for their most complex packaging. Retailers, as key actors in the food value chain, can choose to lead the transition by promoting a fundamental rethinking of their delivery chains. Moving away from the current linear model requires a systemic rethink of how products are delivered to consumers. This must enable a rapid transition to an alternative, sustainable and highly competitive retail system.

R3PACK will contribute to Reduce, Reuse, Rethink PACKaging by securing fast and extensive uptake of industrially relevant, cross-sectorial, cost-effective innovative technologies allowing immediate substitution of complex multilayer plastic packaging with high performing fiber-based packaging. This will be coupled with an economical, industrial and environmental optimisation of reuse schemes demonstrated at large and transnational scale.

R3PACK will be implemented in 3 EU countries by 2 major retailers, covering the needs of 13 different food product types. R3PACK will moreover offer a clear pathway towards a normalised framework for reusable packaging's food safety and for reusable packaging's washing methods, that will serve as reference at EU level. R3PACK will finally offer decision support tools ready to be used by businesses to choose the right packaging solution (between optimised reuse schemes and developed R3PACK paper-based packaging) meeting closely the needs of their products.

2.2. GENERAL APPROVED MESSAGE AND KEYWORDS

The content and messages in this section have been approved by the R3PACK coordinator. They can be used for general publications. Generally, these messages can be helpful for “mass media” publications—articles in magazines, newspapers, radio slots—or for social media content creation.

Any other content or messages **MUST BE SYSTEMATICALLY VALIDATED** by the Action Plan Leader before publishing unless the message consists in:

- 1 – A simple repost of a R3PACK post;
- 2 – A message targeting the specific action of their own organisation within the project, bearing in mind the communication rules detailed in part 3 below.

The approved project message is the following¹:

While packaging waste currently is accountable for 36% of solid waste in EU towns, research shows that reductions can be achieved by focusing on six plastic applications that are projected to account for 86% of the total reduction achievable by 2040, with multilayer/multimaterial packaging constituting the biggest untapped potential.

The R3PACK project's innovative response contributes to Reduce, Reuse, Rethink PACKaging by securing fast and extensive uptake of industrially relevant, cross-sectorial, cost-effective innovative technologies allowing immediate substitution of complex multilayer plastic packaging with high performing fiber-based packaging. Parallely, the project strives to ignite change by building consumer awareness on waste and their environmental and social externalities is driving change, while relying on manufacturers and retailers to lead the transition towards sustainable plastic-free packaging.

Some examples of keywords for positioning and the creation of #hashtags in Social Media platforms are:

R3PACK, Reduce, Reuse, Rethink, Food Packing, Consumer Awareness, Sustainability, Plastic-Free Packaging, Innovation, Horizon Europe, Substitution, Fibre-based packaging, circular economy, packaging standardization, closed loop, ...

3. COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND VISIBILITY

3.1. COMMUNICATION RULES

3.1.1. Visibility of EU funding

¹ Note: the approved message can be tailored to different audiences where necessary. When major changes are included, messages need to be reviewed with SAFE and (RE)SET.

Emblem and funding statement

As laid down by the grant agreement and unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

Funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

The funding statement should be quoted as follows: **“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101060806”**.

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Quality of information - disclaimer

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3.1.2. Internal consortium rules

Graphic chart

All project deliverables and supporting documents must be used the following graphic chart:

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060806. This document reflects the views of the author(s) and does not necessarily reflect the views or policy of the European Commission. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the European Commission shall not be liable for any errors or omissions, however caused. 14

Font	Korolev (titles) Metropolis (text)
Colour of the text (for every material)	Titles: Dark blue #00507f Text: Black #000000 Highlights of critical information: Red #f04132
Title	<u>1. Bold + underlined, font 20</u>
Subtitle	1.1. Bold, font 18
Second level of subtitle	<i>1.1.1., Italic, font 16</i>
Corps	Font 11 or 12
Spacing	1.15
Margins	Standard, i.e.,: High margin : 2 cm. Bottom margin : 3 cm. Left margin : 2,5 cm. Right margin : 2,5 cm. Header : 1,5 cm. Footer : 2 cm
Header	Should feature on the top left-hand corner the R3PACK logo:
Footer	Should feature the EU funding emblem and statement in the middle, and page number at the right-hand corner

Use of the R3PACK logo

In order to increase project visibility and make sure that all affiliated project documents are easily recognised, the project logo should be affixed on all project material (e.g. media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media).

The logo should be featured at the top left-hand corner of document headers or at any place that ensures its visibility for presentations and promotional content (e.g., social media visuals).

3.2. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Project dissemination will occur via both online and offline channels to increase project visibility and outreach.

3.2.1. Online communication

Online channels will include the project website, social media actions and video development and promotion. Together, these groups of actions will help to build a strong Search Engine Optimization (SEO) positioning for the R3PACK project. Quality internal and external links, social media reputation and curated content will be the base of a solid organic online strategy for the project.

News shared will contain, amongst others:

- R3PACK project press releases;
- Announcements of progress;
- Reports on conferences and meetings;
- News of milestone achievements;
- Information about forthcoming events.

SAFE will communicate the main messages of the project agreed in collaboration with the partners coordinators through its social media channels.

Project website

A project website is a dynamic portal with all the key information that the target audiences should receive. It is a practical reference tool; all project partners can refer to it in events or in individual meetings. Besides, content can be easily updated and distributed through online means (e.g. mails or social media).

A project website will be delivered by (RE)SET, the project coordinator, by M3 (late August 2022). The website will be used to communicate on project outputs and findings, as well as project developments throughout the implementation phase. *A project website is a dynamic portal with all the key information that the target audiences should receive. It is a practical reference tool; all project partners can refer to it in events or in individual meetings. Besides, content can be easily updated and distributed through online means (e.g., emails or social media).*

The website will notably feature:

- Home Page: It will include a summary of the project and approach;
- Workplan: This page will show a description of the project's pillars to reach the set goals (objectives, description of actions, context)
- Partners: This page will show a European map locating each partner, including each partner's brief description;
- A news section; an online library, aimed at publishing relevant project documents (e.g., position papers, reports).

Social Media

To increase awareness within civil society, SAFE will develop and coordinate actions on social media. Social networks chosen to spread the activities and results of the projects are:

- Twitter,
- LinkedIn,
- Instagram.

Social Media feeds will be updated and monitored by the WP leader, SAFE, after seeking the approval of the project coordinator ((RE)SET).

All social media posts will ideally be accompanied by visual support (e.g., Canva visual, project graph, short explanatory video).

In order to increase visibility on social media, systematic use of hashtags will be encouraged. Relevant examples to the project include, but are not limited to: #R3PACK, #ReduceReuseRethink, #foodpacking, #Innovation, #plasticfreepackaging, #HorizonEurope.

Depending on the post’s content, the WP leader will strive to tag relevant stakeholders in order to increase outreach. Relevant accounts include project partners or EU institutions. Relevant national entities, such as governmental agencies, producers, retailers, and experts should also be considered on a case-specific basis. In the context of event promotion, speakers should also be tagged (e.g. MEPs).

Table 1: Relevant social network accounts

Entity	Linkedin	Twitter	Instagram
European Commission	European Commission	@EU_Commission	@europeancommission
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)	@EFSA_EU	
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency	@EU_ECHA	
DG SANTE		@EU_HEALTH	
DG ENVI		@EU_ENV	
DG GROW		@EU_GROWTH	
ENVI Committee		@EP_Environment	
IMCO Committee		@EP_SingleMarket	
ITRE Committee		@EP_Industry	

Entity	Linkedin	Twitter	Instagram
Aarhus University	Aarhus University	@AarhusUni_int	
ALTHO BRETS	ALTHO BRETS	@AlthoBrets	@brets_officiel
BIM Kemi	BIM Kemi		
Bioextrax AB	Bioextrax AB		
Carrefour	Carrefour	@CarrefourGroup	@carrefourfrance
Europe Snacks	Europe Snacks France		
Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft	Fraunhofer Institute for Process Engineering and Packaging IVV	@Fraunhofer	
Floréale	Floréale Holding		
GASCOGNE	GASCOGNE: Overview LinkedIn		
GUILLIN	GUILLIN EMBALLAGES		@groupeguillin
Innovhub-Stazioni Sperimentali per l'Industria	Innovhub-Stazioni Sperimentali per l'Industria		
ISTC	ISTC-CNR	@cnr_istc	
Groupe LSDH	Groupe LSDH	@groupeLSDH	@groupeLSDH
Politecnico di Milano	Politecnico di Milano	@Polimi	@Polimi
The (RE)SET Company	The (RE)SET Company		
RISE - Research Institutes of Sweden	RISE Research Institutes of Sweden	@RISEsweden	@risesweden
SAFE - Safe Food Advocacy Europe	SAFE - Safe Food Advocacy Europe	@SafeFoodEurope	
Schreiber Foods	Schreiber Foods		@schreiber_foods
SGS	SGS Agriculture & Food	@SGS_SA	@sgsglobal
SODIAAL	SODIAAL		
Système U	SYSTEME U	@ULesCommercants	@ULesCommercants
THIOLAT PACKAGING	THIOLAT PACKAGING		
Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	@unibo	@unibo

Twitter

R3PACK's twitter feed will be used to disseminate project results and activities online. The overall goal of this platform is to engage with EU policymakers as well as other EU-funded projects in order to increase project visibility and share best practices.

R3PACK's twitter account was launched in M4 (September 2022), once the project visual identity is made available by the project coordinator (expected date: M3).

The posting frequency will be of two to three times a week and can encompass occasional retweets of relevant institutional or news elements.

Instagram

R3PACK's dedicated Instagram account will be used to disseminate project results and activities online and sensitise non-expert audiences to the relevance of plastic-free reusable packaging. This target audience consists in European consumers at large, including younger audiences (with 31.2% of Instagram users are 25-34-year-olds (Instagram, 2022)).

R3PACK's Instagram account will be released around M18, once the first project results and project photos (lab, etc) are made available.

The posting rate for Instagram will be once or twice a week. Aside from creating dedicated visual content, SAFE will strive to make the most of the platform's interactive features in order to create engagement (e.g. use of stories, including polls and quizzes...).

LinkedIn

R3PACK's dedicated LinkedIn account will be used to disseminate project results and activities online and to engage with expert communities, including scientists and researchers.

LinkedIn posts will provide more thorough and scientific information, aiming to post article-like context notes on project results as well as EU regulatory developments.

R3PACK's LinkedIn account is expected to be launched around M4 (September 2022), once the project visual identity is made available by the project coordinator (expected date: M3).

The subchapter will mention both the quantitative and qualitative analytics SAFE (or (RE)SET?) will analyse, as well as the mitigation measures that will be implemented as a result of these analyses.

Newsletter

Lastly, a newsletter will be elaborated and sent by SAFE to inform relevant stakeholders of project implementation and relevant regulatory developments and events via Mailchimp. It will be published every 3 months, for a total number of 12 newsletters.

The newsletter will notably inform recipients of:

- Regulatory developments at EU level,
- Scientific news relevant to the project
- Relevant events and conferences and participation to the most important ones (National events organised by (RE)SET in France, and by Carrefour in Belgium and Spain; an international EU-wide event organised in Brussels by SAFE; virtual roundtables, featuring project partners, consumers, industrials and policymakers; targeted citizens awareness campaigns).

Target audiences for the newsletter include:

- project partners' employees - whether they be directly involved in the project or working in a field or project that is of direct relevance
- partners' clients, subcontractors or partners that are likely to be interested in project development
- relevant consumer organisations and NGOs likely to be interested in the environmental and food safety implications of the project
- EU stakeholders, including Commission civil servants, likely to be interested in project implementation and results, as well as subsequent policy implications.

In order to comply with GDPR rules, SAFE will draft a short email describing the R3PACK project and the purpose of the newsletter. The email will include a link to subscribe to the newsletter. The email will be forwarded to all 24 project partners, who will be in charge of forwarding it to the relevant recipients. The initial subscriber number goal is 200 recipients. The consortium will advertise the newsletter on the website, on social media as well as during project conferences and events. The goal is to reach 400 subscribers by the end of the project.

Press releases

SAFE will send recurrent press releases to relevant EU-based as well as national media. Recipients are based on an internal document comprising over 100 journalists and media originating from at least 6 Member States as well as the UK. Relevant examples include Libération, Le Monde, Euractiv, Politico, AgraFacts, WRBM.

SAFE will strive to send an indicative number of 3 press releases a year, although timing of these press releases will be dependent upon project results and breakthroughs as well as relevant regulatory developments occurring at EU level (e.g., release of position papers, responses to public consultations such as the food contact material regulation, the revision of the Packaging Waste Directive, Proposed bans for dangerous groups of substances (PBTs, PvBv), revision of restrictions on the use of some packaging materials for certain applications such as glass, plastic,...). Dedicated press releases will be sent to announce project launch (M3), project end and main takeaways (M36) as well as following major high-level stakeholder events (M30 & M32).

3.2.2. Offline communication

Printed communication material

To get the broadest audience possible, consumers will also be reached thanks to the publication of communication materials. SAFE plans to publish in-store booklets/flyers and **other printed materials available in retailers' stores** (in Belgium and France). Those booklets/flyers are deemed to be disseminated broadly to reach very large audiences. Further information on this will be provided in the next phase of the project (potentially for the demonstration phase in shops).

Popular science articles

To reinforce the dissemination and the comprehension of the project, at least 10 popular science articles will be published in non-scientific magazines over the duration of the project. They will target investors, technological providers, policy makers, social platforms but also potential end-users and the general public, presenting the scientific benefits of R3PACK innovations.

Events

The following events will be organised by the project consortium:

1. - Project partners will contribute to the organisation of **6 scientific webinars** to present project developments and breakthroughs.
2. - A **high-level stakeholder workshop** will be organised in M30 to present R3PACK's main outcomes will be organised by SAFE, involving EFSA officials, Commission representatives and other relevant stakeholders from the Brussels

network to increase R3PACK visibility at EU level. In particular, SAFE will use the following channels to better reach out EU institutions:

- Several working Group of the European Commission (DG SANTE, DG ENVI, DG GROW);
- EFSA Emerging Risk Working Group;
- EFSA Transparency Regulation Working Group.

A stakeholder workshop will be organised in M30 in Brussels, targeting academics and industrials (for topics such as scientific breakthrough and environmental sustainability), private and public European investors (for future exploitation and scale-up), Policy Makers (for policy making) and the civil society (for public acceptance). The workshop will be also accessible online and recorded to maximize the dissemination through European key stakeholders.

3. - **Demonstrator workshops** will also be organized at the demonstration sites to engage local, regional and European private and public investors and further maximise R3PACK impact.

4. - A **hybrid final conference** will be organised on M32 in the European Parliament by SAFE to present project results and findings and discuss the potential policy paths to improve the food packaging regulatory framework in the EU.

3.3. STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

The purpose of this stakeholder mapping is to identify our social media audience. The tables here below will be reviewed and updated where necessary upon the Action Plan regular reviews.

Table 2: European (and associated countries) food producers

Entity	Country	Contact	Link
Nestlé	Switzerland	+41 21 924 1111	https://www.nestle.com/aboutus/global-presence
LIDL	Germany		https://info.lidl/en
Ferrero	Luxembourg	0800 21042	https://www.ferrero.com/
Danone	France	+33 1 44 35 20 20	https://www.danone.com/about-danone/sustainable-value-creation.html

Table 3: European (and associated countries) relevant wholesalers & retailers

Entity	Country	Contact	Link
AMC Group	Spain	info@amunoz.com	https://www.amcgrupo.eu/en/
EuroCommerc e	Belgium	haiduc@eurocommerce.eu	https://www.eurocommerce.eu/

EDEKA	Germany	info@edeka.de	http://www.edeka.de
European Marketing Distribution	Switzerland	emd@emd.ch	https://www.emd-ag.com/
AUCHAN	France	service-client@auchant.fr	https://www.auchan.fr/

Table 4: European (and associated countries) Representative of the Industry

Entity	Country	Contact	Link
EUROPEN	Belgium	packaging@europen-packaging.eu	https://www.europen-packaging.eu/
European Industrial Packaging Association	Germany	info@eipa-info.eu	http://eipa-info.org/
Food Drink Europe	Belgium	info@fooddrinkeurope.eu	https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu
Food Packaging Forum	Switzerland	info@fp-forum.org	https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/
Beverage Carton Europe – ACE	Belgium	secretariat@beveragecarton.eu	https://www.beveragecarton.eu/
Citeo	France	contact@citeo.com	http://www.citeo.com

Table 5: European (and associated countries) relevant academia targets

Entity	Country	Contact	Link
Université de Liège	Belgium	+32(0)81 62 21 11	https://www.gembloux.uliege.be/cms/c_4039827/fr/gembloux-agro-bio-tech
Università degli Studi di Catania	Italy	+39 (95) 800 644 590	https://www.unict.it/en/
Sapienza - Università di Roma	Italy	+39 064458 5984	https://www.uniroma1.it/it/pagina-strutturale/home
Uniwersytet Rzeszowski	Poland	Poland	jkinal@ur.edu.pl
Universitatea de Stiinte Agronomice si Medicina Veterinara din Bucuresti	Romania	contact@usamvcluj.ro	https://www.usamv.ro/index.php/en/home-eng

Table 6: European (and associated countries) relevant consumers organisations

Entity	Country	Contact	Link
Organización de Consumidores y Usuarios	Spain	informacion@ocu.org	https://www.ocu.org/
Unión de Consumidores de Aragón	Spain	info@ucaragon.com	https://www.ucaragon.com/
European Community of Consumer Cooperatives	Belgium	info@eurocoop.coop	https://www.eurocoop.coop/
DECO	Portugal	deco@deco.pt	https://deco.pt/
Adiconsum	Italy	presidenza.nazionale@adiconsum.it	https://www.adiconsum.it/
ADOC (Associazione Nazionale per la Difesa e l'Orientamento dei Consumatori)	Italy	info@adocnazionale.it adoc@pec.it	https://adocnazionale.it/
The Romande Consumer Federation	Switzerland	+41 21 331 00 90	https://www.frc.ch/
CEIP (Centar za edukaciju i informiranje potrošača)	Croatia	+385 31750106	https://ceip.hr/
Lithuanian Consumer Institute	Lithuania	info@vartotojai.lt	https://www.vartotojai.lt/en/home-english/
InfoCons	Romania	office@infocons.ro	https://infocons.ro/
Union of Working Consumers of Greece	Greece	info@eeke.gr	https://eeke.gr/en/
UFC que choisir	France	https://www.quechoisir.org/nous-contacter-n42652/	https://www.quechoisir.org/

Table 7: European (and associated countries) relevant civil society organisations

Entity	Country	Contact	Link
Zero Waste Europe	Belgium	hello@zerowasteeurope.eu	https://zerowasteeurope.eu
ChemTrust	United Kingdom	askchemtrust@chemtrust.org	https://chemtrust.org/

Table 8: European (and associated countries) relevant reuse key actors

Entity	Country	Contact	Link
ETERNITY SYSTEMS	France		https://eternity-systems.com/
GS1	France		https://www.gs1.fr/
Kennisinstituut Duurzaam Verpakken (KIDV)	The Netherlands	info@kidv.nl	https://kidv.nl/
CU Mehrwegsystem	Germany	info@cu-mehrwegsystem.de	https://www.cu-mehrweg.com/
Options Solutions fr	France		https://www.options-solutions.fr/
Haut Consigne	France	consigne.hdf@lilo.org	https://hautlaconsigne.fr/
Impact Group	France	contact@impact-gr.com	https://impact-gr.com/
Petrel Commerce Circulaire	France	contact@petrel.fr	https://petrel.fr/
Re-uz	France		https://www.reuz.com
Uzaje	France		http://uzaje.com

Table 9: European (and associated countries) relevant packaging manufacturers

Entity	Country	Contact	Link
ELOPAK	Norway	elopak@elopak.com	https://www.elopak.com/packaging-by-nature/
Ecolean	Sweden	info@ecolean.se	https://www.ecolean.com/about/contact/
SEDA International Packaging Group	Italy	+39 081 731 91 11	https://www.sedagroup.com/contact

4. ACTIVITIES

SAFE coordinates the Action Plan of R3PACK and its activities with the involvement of all the partners of the consortium. All partners will creatively seek opportunities to disseminate the project results through their existing communication channels and participate actively to the project dissemination task force.

Calendar

Table 9 provides an indicative timeline of all actions under WP 7. The table will be reviewed every 6 months to adapt where necessary, e.g., adapting publication of press releases upon project results and breakthroughs as well as relevant regulatory developments occurring at EU level, publication of scientific articles, webinar, demonstration workshops.

Activities and KPIs

Activities for 2022

Online activities

- **Creation of online platforms (estimated date M4)**
Through the present Action Plan, SAFE aims to provide the consortium with a complete and detailed action plan for dissemination and exploitation together with appropriate communication activities. This plan includes the creation of a project website and project visual identity ((RE)SET, M3) and of dedicated social media feeds (Twitter, LinkedIn).
- **Creation of a newsletter (M4)**
To inform civil society and consumers, SAFE will publish a newsletter every 3 months, at the exception of M30 and M32, as the newsletter will be dedicated to the event organised within the framework of the project. It will detail the purpose and the activities of the project and provide guidelines to consumers.
- **Technical database/repository (M6)**
To secure access and replicability of data concerning knowledge and innovation development generated throughout the project, data will be stored in a safe European repository. This database is accessible to all stakeholders. The specific management of the R3PACK's digital outputs will be further explained in the Digital Outputs Management Plan at the end of the Action Plan's section.

Offline activities

- **Press releases (M4)**
SAFE will send recurrent press releases to relevant EU-based as well as national media. The first one will be disseminated to present the project. SAFE will strive to send an indicative number of 3 press releases a year, although timing of these press releases will be dependent upon project results and breakthroughs as well as relevant regulatory developments occurring at EU level.
- **Annual report (M7)**
In order to keep the consortium updated with the development of the advocacy strategy, SAFE will share an annual report with the analysis of main achievements and next steps.

Activities for 2023

Online activities

- **Creation of an Instagram account (M12)**
Through the present D&C plan, SAFE aims to provide the consortium with a complete and detailed action plan for dissemination & Exploitation together with appropriate communication activities. This plan includes the creation of a dedicated Instagram profile

Offline activities

- **Scientific publications (throughout the year)**
Depending on scientific developments and project implementation, partners will publish a total of 10 articles in scientific journals to present the outstanding results that are expected to be obtained in the R3PACK project. Open Research

Europe platform will be used to allow a wide and open access to the project peer-reviewed scientific publications.

- **Annual report (M19)**

In order to keep the consortium updated with the development of the advocacy strategy, SAFE will share an annual report with the analysis of main achievements and next steps.

- **R3PACK Business plan - (M12)**

R3PACK Business Plan will be produced as a conclusion in Task 7.3: As a whole, the final project business plan will be produced, showing how profitable it can be for identified private partners and stakeholders to further invest into the project results and adopt them as widely marketed solutions.

- **Development of policy papers, articles and press releases**

As part of the Advocacy Strategy, SAFE will develop policy papers, articles, press releases in line with the most relevant legislative initiatives, notably providing policy recommendations. The latter will focus on the short and medium-term to facilitate the realisation of safe reusable and recyclable food packaging.

An indicative number of 2 policy papers per year will be delivered by SAFE, provided that the regulatory revisions at hand proceed as foreseen in their initial timeline. Besides, 1 article per month will be published on social media.

Work on the following regulatory framework is currently envisioned:

- Revision of the Food Contact Material Regulation;
- Revision of the Packaging Waste Directive;
- Proposed ban for dangerous groups of substances (PBTs, PvBv) such as PFAS and the harmful chemicals;
- Revision of restrictions on the use of some packaging materials for certain applications (glass, bluck, plastic and other materials).

The timeframe and action path specific to each of these legislations is specified in the sections below under Advocacy Strategy.

- **Press releases (M14)**

SAFE will send recurrent press releases to relevant EU-based as well as national media. SAFE will strive to send a number an indicative number of 3 press releases a year, although timing of these press releases will be dependent upon project results and breakthroughs as well as relevant regulatory developments occurring at EU level.

Activities for 2024

Online activities

- **Organisation of 3 webinars**

These events will target scientific communities in order to disseminate the R&D findings.

Offline activities

- **Demonstrator workshops (M28)**
Demonstrator workshops will also be organised at the demonstration sites to engage local, regional and European private and public investors and further maximise R3PACK impact.
- **Organisation of a high-level stakeholders workshop (M30) (hybrid)**
A stakeholder workshop will be organised in Brussels, targeting academics and industrials (for topics such as scientific breakthrough and environmental sustainability), private and public European investors (for future exploitation and scale-up), Policy Makers (for policy making) and the civil society (for public acceptance). The workshop will be also accessible online and recorded to maximise the dissemination through European key stakeholders.
- **Presentations to International events (hybrid)**
At least 8 presentations will be realised within professional fairs/conferences to present the project findings towards industrial, investors and public authorities. Attendance to events such as K fair, Interpack fair, IAPRI conference are also intended.
R3PACK main outcomes will be used and presented at the final conference at the European Parliament.
- **Annual report (M31)**
In order to keep the consortium updated with the development of the advocacy strategy, SAFE will share an annual report with the analysis of main achievements and next steps.
- **Popular science articles (M26-36)**
Depending on scientific developments and project implementation, at least 5 articles will be published in non-scientific magazines (bringing the count to a total of 10). They will target investors, technological providers, policy makers, social platforms but also potential end-users and the general public, presenting the scientific benefits of R3PACK innovations.

Activities for 2025

Online activities

- **Organisation of 3 webinars**
The webinars will target the scientific communities in order to disseminate the R&D findings

Offline activities

- **"What if" scenarios and policy recommendations (M36)**
R3PACK "What if" scenarios and policy recommendations will be developed in Task 7.4. Recommendations will outline potential and plausible scenarios for European development of industrial reuse and substitution of single use plastic for each market studied.
- **Organisation of a final conference in the EP (M32)**
The conference will be held in a hybrid format and will aim to hosting around 500 participants. It will be organised to present project results and to discuss policy pathways on food packaging in the EU.

- Press releases (M33)**
 SAFE will send recurrent press releases to relevant EU-based as well as national media. The first one will be disseminated to present the project. At the end of the project, SAFE will send one dedicated to collecting and snaring the results and data collected during the project. Safe will strive to send an indicative number of 3 press releases a year, although timing of these press releases will be dependent upon project results and breakthroughs as well as relevant regulatory developments occurring at EU level.
- Popular science articles (M26-36)**
 Depending on scientific developments and project implementation, at least 5 articles will be published in non-scientific magazines (bringing the count to a total of 10). They will target investors, technological providers, policy makers, social platforms but also potential end-users and the general public, presenting the scientific benefits of R3PACK innovations.

Table 11: Quantitative analysis of WP7 online communications KPIs

This table will be reviewed every 6 months and updated where necessary.

Target audience	Dissemination activities	Starting month	Indicator to measure the impact	Target Value	Status ²
All target groups (including general public)	R3PACK’s website	M4	Page views	400 pages views	170
	Social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	M4 (except M18 for Instagram)	Number of posts	1 post / week	28
			Number of followers	300 (sum of all social media accounts)	155
	Newsletter	M4	Number of subscriptions	200 subscriptions at M8 – 400 subscriptions at M36	62
Number of newsletters			12 newsletters	1	

² Status as of M6.

ADVOCACY STRATEGY

5. INTRODUCTION

R3PACK is relevant for several streams of the European Green Deal. The sustainable and safe packaging solutions that the project will develop for reuse and substitution will not only be relevant for the objectives of the EU Circular Economy Action Plan and Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, but also for the upcoming revisions of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive and the Food Contact Materials Regulation. These policies represent an outstanding opportunity to make sure the EU delivers a legal framework providing social and environmental protection and legal accountability, as well as incentivising innovation and investment.

Moreover, R3PACK core findings covering both reuse and substitution will be used to contribute to the definition of the future EU framework for sustainability labelling. The Food Safety Protocol and the Washing Protocols (WP3) will constitute strategic tools, ready to be used to support new policy initiatives around industrial reuse uptake.

Within this framework, R3PACK will involve advocacy campaigns focused on initiatives aiming at promoting alternative sustainable food packaging and prevent harmful chemicals to get into contact with food contact materials (*substitution*), as well as campaigns addressing issues connected with recyclability, safety and sustainability (*reuse*). R3PACK will also produce technical reports (based on the results from WP2, Task 2.2 and WP3, Task 3.2) addressed to EFSA, ECHA and the European Commission.

6. OBJECTIVE

The goal of this advocacy strategy is to influence the outcome of the legislation during the running of R3PACK to:

- Call on the Commission to establish ambitious and binding waste prevention and reuse targets, while promoting sustainable food contact materials in packaging with special focus on paper-based packaging;
- Use the Reuse standardised model developed in the project (WP3, Task 3.3) as an example of best practices for a broader application at EU level;
- Stimulate reusable packaging through the revision of the essential requirements for packaging under Packaging Waste Directive that should lead to ambitious legislation with a strong focus on design for reuse, toxic -free materials and recyclability.

R3PACK will work toward the above goals by actively following and contributing to relevant regulatory developments occurring at EU level (based on the outcomes of Task 2.2 (WP2)) and developing specific recommendations to facilitate the standardization of safe food packaging and the reusable food packaging and the adoption of paper-based packaging based on the results of the demonstration process (Task 5.6, WP5)).

Identified initiatives

Based on the outcomes of Task 2.2 (WP2), the below EU regulatory initiatives have been identified as the most relevant opportunities to work towards the Advocacy Strategy objectives.

1. *Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive*

The Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive 94/62/EC (Packaging Directive) regulates the placing on the market of packaging as well as packaging waste prevention and management. All packaging placed on the EU market has to comply with essential requirements relating to its composition and reusable and recoverable nature.

There is a limited competitiveness of secondary materials from recycled packaging. Demand for secondary materials from recycled packaging remains too low, resulting in valuable resources being lost to the economy: only a limited share of the packaging waste is recycled and finds its way back into new products or packaging. The main obstacles to a strong market are thought to include their higher costs relative to virgin feedstock, and the limited availability of stable quantities and high-quality secondary materials. Moreover, this situation is exacerbated by the lack of clear legal rules requiring that packaging can be recycled to high quality in a cost-efficient way. Current trends on the packaging market show an increase in difficult-to-recycle packaging such as flexible multilayer composite packaging. Current essential requirements for packaging, dating back to 1994, do not provide the regulatory push for design changes for re-use and recyclability as they are not fully aligned with the waste hierarchy. The essential requirements also leave too much room to interpretation, in particular about what qualifies as recyclable. This has in particular spurred a trend towards light-weighting of packaging, sometimes at the expense of recyclability.

The revision of the Packaging Directive aims at reviewing the requirements on packaging and packaging waste in the EU to: improve packaging design to promote reuse and recycling, increase recycled content in packaging, tackle excessive packaging, and reduce packaging waste.

The initiative will amend the essential requirements to improve design for reuse and promote high quality recycling, as well as additional measures to reduce packaging waste generation and may include the setting of targets. These targets and measures may be general or set at the level of a specific material or packaging formats, and may include making reuse mandatory for some packaging formats.

Other measures that will also be examined in the context of this initiative will include:

- requiring all packaging to be reusable or recyclable and providing an enforceable definition of ‘recyclable packaging’;
- restricting the use of some packaging materials to certain applications, in particular where alternative reusable products or systems are possible or consumer goods can be handled safely without packaging;
- reducing the complexity of packaging materials including the number of material and polymers used;
- introducing recycled content targets for specific packaging formats;

The Commission is expected to publish proposal for legislation on 30th November. R3PACK will publish a **press release** acknowledging the proposal and highlighting key aspects where the outcome of the project can influence and improve the proposal. At

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a later stage, once R3PACK results are available, a **position paper** will be developed with specific recommendations developed together with the relevant R3PACK partners.

2. Food Contact Materials revision

The Food Contact Materials Regulation ((EC) No 1935/2004) sets basic EU rules for all food contact materials (FCMs), which aims to secure a high level of protection of human health, protect the interests of consumers and ensure that the internal market functions effectively.

The Regulation requires FCMs to be manufactured so that chemical substances do not migrate into food that would endanger human health and sets other rules such as those on labelling and traceability. It also allows specific rules to be introduced for particular materials and establishes a process for the risk assessment of substances by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and eventual authorisation by the Commission. This has been achieved primarily for plastic FCMs³, whereby compositional requirements and a list of authorized substances together with certain restrictions such as migration limits, have been established. For many other materials, such as paper and cardboard, metal and glass materials, adhesives, coatings, silicones and rubber, specific rules do not exist at EU level and national legislation may apply.

Moreover, the current FCM legislation provides little or no basis on which to develop rules that support and encourage sustainable alternatives to packaging or ensure these alternatives are safe. Many legacy materials and substances were authorised based on a less stringent risk assessment, while new materials and substances are subject to a steadily increasing level of scrutiny. This de-incentivises innovation. Moreover, recyclability of all materials and new technologies such as chemical recycling must be addressed in order for the EU to reach its ambitious recycling objectives.

The revision aims to modernize its rules to, among others, reduce the presence and use of hazardous chemicals, take account of the latest science and technology, and support innovation and sustainability by promoting safe reusable and recyclable solutions, and help reduce the sector's environmental impact.

Among the policy options, the Commission is looking into introducing specific rules to ensure that FCMs manufactured from less traditional and potentially more sustainable production sources and methods are subject to dedicated and clear rules on safety to incentivise their use. In addition, the Commission would expand rules to prioritise and support all forms of safe reuse and recycling, to exclude risk from contamination and to include all recycling technologies. Rules would also support sustainability of food packaging through their entire life-cycle.

As part of the ongoing initiative, the Commission has launched a public consultation running until 11th January. R3PACK will publish a **press release** on the public consultation to stress the relevance of the ongoing work under R3PACK and the need for the future revised legislation to properly address less traditional and more sustainable production sources and methods like fibre-based substrates.

³ Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food (OJ L 12, 15.1.2011).

We will monitor the initiative as well as upcoming proposal (planned by Q2 2023) with the aim of developing a **position paper** with specific recommendations developed together with the relevant R3PACK partners.

3. Waste Framework Directive revision

The Waste Framework Directive (WFD) establishes a waste hierarchy that favours the prevention of waste over (in order) preparing for re-use; recycling; other waste recovery options; and disposal of waste. The WFD requires Member States to take measures to prevent the generation of waste and to collect certain types of waste separately. It also provides for review clauses on prevention measures, food waste, and waste oils.

This initiative aims to improve the overall environmental outcome for good waste-management in line with the waste hierarchy and the implementation of the polluter pays principle. The initiative's objectives are to:

- Decree waste generation,
- Improve separate waste collection to yield optimal recycling results, incl. by avoiding contamination of recyclable waste,
- Increase the amounts of waste oils collected and treated.

The following options are being considered by the Commission:

- Promote full implementation of the provisions on waste prevention, preparation for re-use and recycling (e.g. enhanced cooperation with Member States and enforcement);
- Provide additional guidance, e.g. clarify and explain in detail waste-prevention provisions;
- Consider regulatory measures to:
 - Reduce waste generation by introducing overall and/or product-specific prevention measures, incl. targets on waste reduction and expanding the role of extended producer responsibility (EPR) schemes;
 - Reinforce the polluter pays principle by expanding EPR schemes to other product categories, like textiles and oils;
 - Set waste oil collection and regeneration targets.

This initiative will integrate the initiative for the reduction of food waste⁴.

A proposal for a Directive is planned for Q2 2023. R3PACK will publish a **press release** acknowledging the proposal and highlighting key aspects where the outcome of the project on reuse can influence and improve the proposal.

4. Proposed ban for dangerous groups of substances (PBTs, PvBv)

⁴ See EC initiative: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13223-Food-waste-reduction-targets_en

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)

In 2021 five countries (Germany, Denmark, Netherlands, Norway and Sweden) submitted to ECHA an intention for a restriction dossier on Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). The aim is to ban the use of the entire group of PFAS substances in Europe. The countries are currently working on the restriction proposal, to be submitted to ECHA by 13th January 2023. Subsequently, a public consultation will be launched and the ECHA Scientific Committees (RAC and SEAC) will prepare their opinions. In the final stage, the European member states will decide whether to adopt the proposal.

R3PACK will monitor the process and publish **press releases** where relevant (i.e. publication of proposal, launch of public consultation, final decision on proposal) to advocate for a ban on all PFAS substances. If possible, R3PACK will assess contributing to the future public consultation.

Intentionally added microplastics

The European Green Deal, the new Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) and the EU Plastics Strategy announce measures to tackle pollution from microplastics that are intentionally added to products (e.g. cosmetics, detergents, paints) and those that are unintentionally released into the environment (from e.g. tyres and synthetic textiles). In particular, the measures intend to:

- Restrict intentionally added microplastics taking into account ECHA opinions;
- Develop labelling, standardization, certification and regulatory measures on unintentional release of microplastics, including to increase the capture of microplastics at all relevant stages of products' lifecycle (see section below);
- Further develop and harmonise methods to measure unintentionally released microplastics.

In August 2022, the Commission published a draft regulation⁵ to restrict microplastics in products placed on the EU/EEA market to avoid their release to the environment. The draft would restrict microplastics under REACH Annex XVII. The proposal is currently being discussed with Member State authorities pending a vote (2022-2023); if positive, the proposal will go to the Council and European Parliament for final approval.

R3PACK will monitor this process and provide feedback where possible, advocating to restrict the amount of microplastics released into the environment. A **press release** will be considered to stress the later and to highlight the current work undergoing at R3PACK.

5. Revision of restrictions on the use of some packaging materials for certain applications (glass, plastic and other materials)

⁵ See draft Regulation here: [Comitology Register \(europa.eu\)](https://comitology-register.europa.eu)

Unintentionally added microplastics

In November 2021, the Commission launched an initiative to tackle unintentionally released microplastics from tyres, textiles and plastic pallets – a proposal for a Regulation is expected by Q4 2022.

While food contact materials are not within the scope of this initiative, R3PACK will monitor the process and advocate, where possible, to restrict the amount of microplastics released into the environment, and to showcase the potential of using alternative solutions (e.g. providing data on microplastic release of the project solutions, WP4 Task 4.6).

REACH and CLP

The REACH Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of chemicals (Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006), together with the CLP Regulation on Classification, Labelling and Packaging (Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008) of chemicals, are the key Union legislation for the assessment and management of chemicals.

In 2021, the Commission launched initiatives to review the REACH and CLP legislations.

1.- REACH: The REACH revision aims to address identified issues in a 2018 evaluation⁶. The Commission is looking into, among other, reforming the authorisation and the restriction processes. The revision is looking into:

- Reviewing the registration requirements, including increased information on hazards of concerns, documentation of safe use, registration of certain polymers, and information on the environmental footprint;
- Introducing of a Mixtures Assessment Factor (MAF), to address the risk of exposure to several substances (combination effects);
- Simplifying communication in the supply chains;
- Reviewing the provisions for dossier and substance evaluation;
- Reforming the authorisation process – options include clarifications and simplifications of the current provisions, national authorisation for smaller applications, removing the authorisation title from REACH, integrating the REACH authorisation and restriction systems into one and improving the interface with other pieces of legislation;
- Reforming the restriction process, where one of the policy options explores extending the generic risk approach to restrictions to endocrine disruptors, PBT/vPvB substances; and operationalising the concept of essential use in restrictions, including the criteria for granting derogations;
- Reviewing provisions for control and enforcement.

A proposal for legislation is planned for Q1 2023.

2.- CLP: The CLP revision aims to keep up with scientific, technological and (on-line) market developments, as well as to tackle some identified issues such as the incomplete information about hazards to human health and the environment, hindrance

⁶ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council and the European Economic and Social Committee on Commission General Report on the operation of REACH and review of certain elements. Conclusions and Actions (COM/2018/0116 final).

of the free circulation of chemicals in the internal market, and insufficient public resources.

In doing so, the Commission will look into, among other measures:

- Introducing new hazard classes (such as endocrine disruptors) and corresponding criteria;
- Introducing an obligation to provide information of some hazards on the label of products currently outside the scope of CLP;
- Clarify the obligations to classify mixtures and some complex substances;
- Introducing the possibility to submit proposals for and set harmonised environmental and safety values for some substances;
- Requesting ECHA to develop new harmonised classification and labelling dossiers.

A proposal for regulation was planned for Q2 2022 but has been delayed.

R3PACK will monitor the two initiatives advocating for a legislation with a strong focus on a toxic-free environment. A **press release** upon the publication of the regulations will be considered to highlight the current work undergoing at R3PACK and the work towards a toxic-free environment. Based on R3PACK outcomes, a **position paper** will be considered.

Persistent Organic Pollutants

In October 2021, the Commission published a proposal for regulation amending Annexes IV and V to Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 on persistent organic pollutants (POPs Regulation⁷). The revision aims to address the negative consequences of the presence of certain POPs substances in waste and in material that could be recovered from it, ensuring that such waste is managed in an environmentally sound way and that it achieves safer recycling.

The revision is to introduce limit values under Annexes IV and V for new substances:

- pentachlorophenol, its salts and esters, found in treated wood and textiles
- dicofol, which is a pesticide previously used in agriculture
- perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), its salts and PFOA-related compounds, found in waterproof textiles and fire-fighting foams.

In October 2022, the EP and Council adopted their positions in first reading under the ordinary legislative procedure. The act is currently awaiting signatures to become legislation. While there is no longer an opportunity to influence this legislation, R3PACK will monitor the publication and publish a **press release**. Pending on the outcomes of R3PACK, a **position paper** will be considered in the future.

⁷ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL amending Annexes IV and V to Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 of the European Parliament and of the Council on persistent organic pollutants (COM/2021/656 final)

EU Framework for Sustainable Food Systems

In 2021, the Commission launched its initiative on the EU Framework for Sustainable Food Systems (FSFS). This initiative aims to make the EU food system sustainable and to integrate sustainability into all food-related policies – in essence, to ensure that all foods placed on the EU market increasingly become sustainable. This implies building a socially responsible food value chain that progressively reduces the environmental and climate footprint of the Union food system, and ultimately transform the EU food system into a more sustainable one.

The framework will lay down general principles and objectives, together with the requirements and responsibilities of all actors in the EU food system. It will also lay down rules on sustainability labelling of food products to empower consumers to make more sustainable food choices.

R3PACK core findings covering both reuse and substitution will be used to contribute to the definition of the future EU framework for sustainability labelling.

A proposal for legislation is planned by Q3 2023. R3PACK will monitor this process and influence where possible. A **press release** upon the publication will be considered to highlight the current work undergoing at R3PACK. A **position paper** developing on the definition of sustainability labelling will be developed once relevant deliverables are completed.

7. TARGETS - STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

The purpose of this stakeholder mapping is to identify key EU policy and decision-makers to which R3PACK can forward our press releases, position papers and recommendations. Where appropriate and if possible, during the running of the project, R3PACK will try to influence ordinary legislative procedure of identified initiatives by organizing meetings with Members of the European Parliament (MEPs).

Appendix I provides an extensive mapping of the identified relevant EU bodies. The mapping and tables here below provide a more targeted list of contacts to reach out to during the next months. The stakeholder mapping will be updated accordingly to identify key MEPs and Council contacts for the specific initiatives, as well as to include new contacts acquired in the coming months.

European Commission

As the EU institution tabling laws for adopting by the Parliament and the Council, and in charge of the preparatory work ahead of the publication of a legislative proposal, the European Commission is a relevant stakeholder with whom to engage and forward our data and materials. R3PACK's outcomes and advocacy materials will serve as a tool in developing future legislation.

The relevant Directorates-General (DGs) and units therein identified are the following:

Table 12: European Commission mapping

DG	Unit	Contact	Details
DG SANTE	Unit E2 (Food processing technologies and novel foods)	Mr Bruno Gautrais, Head of Unit	bruno.gautrais@ec.europa.eu +3222956465 SANTE-DG@ec.europa.eu
	Unit E1 (Farm to Fork)	Ms Alexandra Nikolakopoulou, Head of Unit	Alexandra.nikolakopoulou@ec.europa.eu +3222986854
DG ENV	Unit B1 (Sustainable Production, products and consumption)	Ms Emmanuelle Maire, Head of Unit	Emmanuelle.maire@ec.europa.eu +3222991586
		Mr Werner Bosmans, Policy Office – Circular Economy	Werner.bosmans@ec.europa.eu +3222967282
	Unit B3 (From Waste to Resources)	Mr Mattia Pellegrini, Head of Unit	Matia.pellegrini@ec.europa.eu +3222954138
DG GROW	Unit I3 (Green and circular transition)	Mr Stefano Soro, Head of Unit	Stefano.soro@ec.europa.eu +3222967543

European Parliament

The European Parliament (EP) is one of the two EU's law-making body, together with the Council of the EU. The EP works in committees, each handling a particular policy area. The Committees examine proposals for legislation - an MEP within the committee is appointed as rapporteur to present a draft report on the proposal. MEPs and political groups can put forward amendments or propose to reject a bill. During plenary sessions all the MEPs gather in the chamber to give a final vote on the EP position on the matter.

The identified relevant EP committees for R3PACK are the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety Committee (ENVI), and the Internal Market and Consumer Protection Committee (IMCO). A detailed table with relevant MEPs will be developed during the first revision of the Action Plan, once the first Commission proposals are sent to the relevant committees and the rapporteur and shadow rapporteurs are named. R3PACK will focus its advocacy efforts on contacting rapporteurs and shadow rapporteurs.

Council Presidency

The Council is the main decision-maker together with the EP. Each EU country holds the presidency of the body on a 6-month rotating basis. The presidencies during the life of R3PACK are the following:

- Czech Republic (July-December 2022)
- Sweden (January-June 2023)
- Spain (July-December 2023)
- Belgium (January-June 2024)

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- Hungary (July-December 2024)
- Poland (January-June 2025)

The Council meets in ten different configurations, each responding to the policy area being discussed. The identified relevant configurations for R3PACK are Environment Council configuration (ENV), and Employment, Social Policy, Health and Consumer Affairs Council configuration (EPSCO).

A detailed table with relevant ENV and EPSCO officers from the current presidency at the time will be reviewed and updated where necessary. R3PACK will focus its advocacy efforts on contacting officers from the upcoming presidencies, as of M6 this is the Swedish presidency.

Table 13: Swedish Permanent Representation to the EU mapping

Configuration	Contact	Details
ENV	Mr Patrik Brodd, Counsellor – Working Party on the Environment, Waste, Circular Economy and Chemicals	patrik.brodd@gov.se +32479591411 representationen.bryssel@gov.se
EPSCO	Ms Elizabeth Ekenstaf, Counsellor	elizabeth.ekenstaf@gov.se +3222895847
	Ms Karolina Schlyter, Counsellor	karolina.schlyter@gov.se +3222895725
	Mr Joakim Svensson, Councillor	joakim.svensson@gov.se +3222895719

EFSA

The European Food Safety Agency (EFSA) provides independent scientific advice on food-related risks. EFSA issues advice on existing and emerging risks, which informs European laws, rules and policymaking – and so helps protect consumers from risks in the food chain.

EFSA’s work involves, among others, gathering scientific data and expertise, providing independent, up-to-date scientific advice on food safety issues, and cooperating with EU countries, international bodies and other stakeholders. EFSA has different engagement mechanisms with stakeholders, including the EFSA Stakeholder Discussion Group on Emerging Risks (StaDG-ER).

Through SAFE, which is a member of the abovementioned EFSA stakeholder group, R3PACK will share its results and outcomes with EFSA to work towards our advocacy objectives.

ECHA

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) works for the safe use of chemicals. It implements the EU's chemicals legislation – it develops independent scientific and technical opinions and takes binding decisions to ensure that chemicals companies

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comply with EU law. Its scientific advice informs the Commission on hazards and risks of chemicals, their impact on society and ways to mitigate their risks.

ECHA cooperates with international organisations and stakeholders to promote safe use of chemicals. R3PACK will share its technical reports with ECHA to work towards our advocacy objectives.

8. KEY MESSAGES

The main key messages of R3PACK will be fine-tuned and further developed during its own development once Work Packages have produced outcomes and deliverables are completed. Furthermore, A first collection of messages are shown below:

- **Elimination, substitution and expansion of consumer reuse options is the optimum solution to achieve an immediate reduction of plastic pollution.** It allows the biggest reduction in plastic pollution and provides the highest mitigation opportunity in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions compared to existing alternative system interventions (such as mechanical recycling or plastic chemical conversion).
- **EU legislation needs to be updated to promote alternative sustainable food packaging and prevent harmful chemicals to get into contact with food.**
- **The uptake of reuse schemes is key in reducing packaging waste at the source.** EU legislation needs to support the uptake of reuse schemes that prevent the need to dispose. R3PACK outcomes propose the right packaging for the right products with the right washing and return logistics strategies adapted to local context, as well as a model for collaboration between players to implement reuse.
- **Fibre-based packaging can substitute/should be promoted to substitute complex multilayer plastic packaging.** Paper and coated paper are among the most prevalent materials available today for replacing problematic and complex plastic films and multilayer flexibles. R3PACK outcomes demonstrate how fibre-based solutions can fully replace plastic linings with biobased barrier coatings and additives.

R3PACK key messages will be enshrined in the outcomes of the WPs/data. However, these will need to be turned into simple, short, and easy messages. When supportive evidence is available, it is important to provide real-life cases so that these are easy to understand by our targets and so that they can use these to convince their colleagues.

When advocacy campaigns start our key messages need to be repeated throughout our social media activity, position papers, press releases, etc.

9. KEY INDICATORS PERFORMANCE & CALENDAR

This section provides a summary of EU advocacy actions, KPIs and timeline. Actions include policy papers (based policy recommendation as developed under Task 7.4), press releases and articles.

The below table will be reviewed and amended where necessary to adapt to any delays (e.g. publications of EU proposals), include new actions in light of new R3PACK results, and maximise the impact of our actions. Meetings with MEPs and Commission

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officials will be considered in the context of initiatives under the ordinary legislative procedure, and subject to R3PACK already having outputs that can be shared and influence the initiative in question. Further information on this will be provided with every revision of the Action Plan.

Timeline information will be included in Table 9 insofar as possible.

Table 14: EU advocacy actions, KPIs and timeline

Type of action	KPIs	Details	(Tentative) Timeline ⁸
Press releases	7	Packaging & Packaging Waste proposal publication	M7
		Food Contact Materials (FCMs) public consultation	M8
		FCMs proposal publication	M14
		Ban on PFAS	M14 to M19
		Ban on intentionally added microplastics	M14 to M19
		EU Framework for Sustainable Food Systems proposal publication	M16
		REACH proposal and CLP proposal publications	M11
		Waste Framework Directive revision	M14
Position papers	6 ⁹	Packaging & Packaging Waste proposal	M12 to M36
		FCMs proposal	M12 to M36
		Unintentionally added microplastics	M12 to M36
		EU Framework for Sustainable Food Systems – sustainable labelling	M16 to M36
		Waste Framework Directive proposal	M14 to M36
		Call for harmonised EU rules on fibre-based material (<i>R3PACK own-initiative</i>)	M26 to M36

⁸ Note: deadline is indicated as tentative due to two factors: EC timelines are often expressed in year quarters; content of planned activities depends on the conclusion of R3PACK working packages and their outcomes.

⁹ Indicative number provided that the regulatory revisions at hand proceed as foreseen in their initial timeline.

Articles	30	Content of articles will depend on the project developments, outcomes of the different work packages and tasks	M6 to M36
Meetings with EU officials	6	R3PACK will aim to meet with MEPs and Council representatives to discuss R3PACK outcomes in the context of relevant regulatory revisions ¹⁰	M6 to M36
Final conference at the European Parliament	1	R3PACK main outcomes will be used and presented at roundtable at the EP involving EFSA officials, Commission representatives and other relevant stakeholder	M32

CONCLUSIONS

The Action Plan in the framework of WP 7 of the R3PACK project further elaborates on the project’s target audiences as well as on the tailored actions and channels to engage with them and ensure timely and adequate project visibility, outreach and efficacy. Moreover, it provides information on advocacy actions, digital outputs or key performance indicators. Further detail will notably be provided on advocacy document topics and dissemination, as well as on the digital outputs management plan (DOMP).

¹⁰ Provided that regulatory revisions at hand proceed as foreseen in their initial timeline.

DOMP

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Following Horizon Europe's position on Open Access and as per Annex 5 of Grant Agreement about specific rules on Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility (Article 17), the digital outputs emerging from R3PACK's Research and Innovation project will be made publicly available when possible. Certain contents may be limited by intellectual property rights, their accessibility will be managed specifically with the owner or joint owners. Sensitive information will remain confidential.

INTRODUCTION

As required by Horizon Europe and according to project guidelines advocating for Open Science, R3PACK engages in not only making scientific publications publicly available, but also as advised:

- all data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications
- any other data
- other information about the tools used within the project to achieve current results (algorithms, surveys, analysis protocols),

as will be described in the following Digital Output Management Plan – DOMP.

The open access to R3PACK's data will allow to foster the cross-industry uptake of the newly developed solutions, as often the lack of dissemination slows down the innovation process within a sector. The digital outputs dissemination will contribute to promoting a systemic approach to how to best design, process and commercialize new sustainable packaging.

1. DATA SUMMARY

1.1. DATA GENERATION

Digital outputs will mainly consist in quantitative and qualitative digital information produced during research activities from the Universities, Laboratories and Technology providers - partner of the project. It encompasses all digital outputs related to the 25 deliverables due in the project's lifetime, all data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications and more.

For instance, Aarhus will conduct a consumer behavior study through surveys and in-depth interviews, which will be confirmed by real-life observation during the demonstration phase of the project. Unibo will create an algorithm that allows to optimize the logistic paths of a reuse model, through the different nodes.

1.2. DATA REUSE

Open science is key to helping the research community tackling society's challenges (cure for cancer, astronomy discovery...). In R3PACK's case digital outputs and results will contribute to accelerate the reduction of single-use plastic packaging put to market and consequently plastic pollution.

R3PACK's open-source research and innovation will allow researchers and scientists to have a ground basis at hand, for instance on fibre-based solutions as alternatives to plastic, which they can build on. It can also favour transfer of technology, boosting cross-industry research.

Industrials across Europe will benefit from the data as well. It will help them in their decision making towards transitioning from single-use plastic to more sustainable solutions, either reuse or alternative packaging. The Open Access of output data will secure dissemination and uptake of results for a greater impact within the food industry primarily, but also across industries throughout Europe.

Citizens will have access to informed studies enlightening them about the challenges of packaging and how their behaviour, when purchasing and disposing of packaging, can improve society's environmental impact.

Ultimately, it will smoothen and shorten the process for reducing, reusing, and rethinking single use plastic packaging in the EU.

2. DIGITAL OUTPUT MANAGEMENT

2.1. OPEN SCIENCE & FAIR PRINCIPLES

Open Sciences principles will be fully embraced to allow replicability of R3PACK's research results. Accordingly, all Digital Outputs such as algorithms, surveys, interviews, observation, processes, analysis, which are key to the understanding and picking up of solutions, will be made accessible, when possible, to ensure the European-wide exploitation of results.

Digital outputs will be published in accordance with the FAIR principles, ensuring their findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

2.2 FINDABLE

Zenodo is the designated repository for R3PACK and shall host all public data generated throughout the project, including Digital outputs. The data will be findable as metadata will be provided to allow discovery and be assigned a digital object identifier, as further described in the Digital Management Plan (DMP) (*see DMP Part 2, 2.1*).

2.3 ACCESSIBILITY

2.3.1 Accessible data

As per the Grant Agreement, open peer review of R3PACK scientific publications will be made fully accessible. In addition, for the purpose of European-wide systemic change, R3PACK has agreed to grant access to the results foundations including:

- Main hypotheses of experimental work conducted in WP2, WP3, WP4 and primary statistical analyses will be pre-registered.
- Data and analysis code will be made publicly accessible after publication.

Full open access will be provided to 23 out of 25 of R3PACK's deliverables. All these deliverables will be fully accessible to enable a broader impact of the project's results. The only restricted deliverables will be D2.1 and D4.1. They will be registered as sensitive, and their access will be limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement, as further explained in the DMP (*see DMP Part 2.2.1*).

In the same way all related digital outputs linked to the 23 public deliverables will be openly accessible through a secured repository.

2.3.2 Repository

The digital outputs will be deposited in the trusted European repository Zenodo, hosted by CERN, an intergovernmental organisation, founded in 1954. The repository is partly funded by the European Commission via the OpenAIRE projects (e.g. FP7: OpenAIRE (246686); Horizon 2020: OpenAIRE2020 (643410), ...). Cern's servers are stored in Europe, ensuring the respect of European laws, for instance with regards to GDPR.

Zenodo hosts the community "R3PACK", which allows to safely share and store the consortium's data and manage its visibility.

Open access to publications raw data, output data, software, models, algorithms, workflows etc will be granted to the public through the repository.

2.4 INTEROPERABILITY

The repository in which the digital outputs will be deposited will ensure interoperability by including qualified references to metadata and using metadata vocabulary that follows fair principles as explained in the DMP (*see DMP part 2.3*).

2.5 REUSABILITY

In addition to the results, data analytics source code, and the datasets, will be published in order to facilitate reproducibility. R3PACK will also comply with the Open Research Data Pilot to increase chances of reuse. As described on OpenAire (<https://www.openaire.eu/find-trustworthy-data-repository>) it requires to upload on a research data repository following data:

- "all data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, including the metadata that describe the research data deposited as soon as possible
- any other data (for instance curated data not directly attributable to a publication, or raw data), including the associated metadata, as soon as possible
- projects should also provide information via the chosen repository about the tools that are needed to validate the results, e.g. specialised software or software code, algorithms and analysis protocols."

A quality protocol, including a quality check and publishing policy, will ensure the revision of all collected data from the partners, to assure its comprehensiveness, reusability and open access (see DMP part 2.4.2).

Figure 1 – R3PACK Quality Assurance Process

2.6 Other

Allocation of resources and data security will be managed as described in the DMP (see part. 4 and 5).

CONCLUSION

All datasets, including digital outputs, when possible, will be stored in the unique European repository Zenodo to allow their open access and foster reusability of R3PACK’s results. Management of data and digital outputs will therefore be similar and explained in further detail in the Digital Management Plan.

REFERENCES

Website of Zenodo: <https://about.zenodo.org/>

Horizon Europe webinar on opens science: <https://www.horizon-europe.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/2021-06/lancementheu-fr-webnr-jf05-transv-sc-ouv-3182.pdf>

Website of OpenAire: <https://www.openaire.eu/find-trustworthy-data-repository>

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